

**AN AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF CORNEAL DISORDERS W.S.R. TO
KERATOCONUS: A SINGLE CASE STUDY**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Keratoconus is a progressive non-inflammatory bilateral ectatic condition of cornea in its axial part. it is disorder in which central corneal stromal thinning occurs, accompanied by apical protrusion and irregular astigmatism. It is diagnosed by clinical examination and corneal topographic techniques. Management of keratoconus includes contact lens and keratoplasty. Based on symptoms it can be correlated with Pratama patalagata timira of Vata dosha predominance. **Materials and Methods:** In this case report, a 23year old male patient was diagnosed as keratoconus and underwent Ayurvedic treatment protocol according to the line of management of Prathama patalagata timira which is vatahara and bhramhna in nature. shirovirechana with anutaila, & tarpana with Jeevantyadi Ghrita followed by oral medicationfor 30days. He showed signs of visual improvement after treatment. **Result:** After 2 months of treatment there was a significant reduction in the signs and symptoms of the disease with a better improvement in the condition. **Conclusion:** the present case study shows the efficacy of ayurveda intervention including both external and internal medications applied following the treatment strategy as perprinciples of ayurveda mentioned in classical text books.

KEYWORDS: Keratoconus, Prathama patalagata timira, Shirovirechana, Netra tarpan Netrakriyakalpa, Chakshushya aushadhi, shaman chikitsa.

INTRODUCTION

Keratoconus, derives from the Greek words Kerato (cornea) and Konos (cone). Keratoconus is the most common primary ectasia. It is a bilateral and asymmetric corneal degeneration characterized by localized corneal thinning which leads to protrusion of the thinned cornea. or Keratoconus is a corneal disorder in which the central portion of cornea becomes thinner and bulges forward in a cone shaped fashion resulting in myopia, irregular astigmatism and visual impairment.^[1] it is a challenging eye condition that can affect the vision and the quality of life.

Approximately 50% of normal fellow eyes will progress to Keratoconus within 16 years. Both eyes are affected eventually.^[1,2]

In Ayurveda, there is no direct reference for keratoconus, but based on the symptoms, it can be considered as *Timira*, a *Drishtigata Roga* or disease that affects the vision. *Timira* is further classified into four types according to the involvement of *DoshasVataja*, *Pittaja*, *Kaphaja*, and *Raktaja*. Among these, *vataja timira* and *Prathama patalagata timira* is the most relevant for keratoconus, as it is characterized by *Vyavidhha Darsana* (curved appearance of a straight line), *Avila Darshana* (blurred vision or hazy vision), *Chandra*, *Deepadya Anekatvam* (the luminous objects like moon, lamp appear to be multiple), and *Kshina driushti* (diminished vision).^[3,4] However, the symptoms of myopia and irregular astigmatism seen in the condition may allow comparison with *Timira* and *Kaca*. According to *Acharya Susruta* and *Vagbhata*, *Timira* and *Kaca* are *Dristigata Rogas* (diseases of vision). *Timira* is when

the *Doshas*(humors) goes into the 3rd *Paṭala* (layer) according to *Acharya Susruta*. *Acarya Vagbhata* explains *Timira* as the condition in which the *Doshas* goes into the 2nd *Patala*, and *Kaca* when the 3rd *Paṭala* is afflicted. Diminished distant vision, the cardinal feature of myopia and astigmatism, is seen in *Timira*.^[5,6]

If *Timira* is not treated in time it leads to *Linganasha*, it is better to intervene at the earliest to arrest the further progression of disease. and Keratoconus deals with modern management varies depending on the disease severity. Traditionally, incipient cases are managed with spectacles, mild to moderate cases with contact lenses, and severe cases can be treated with keratoplasty. Other surgical treatment options include intra-corneal rings segments, corneal cross-linking, laser procedures (i.e., photorefractive keratectomy, phototherapeutic keratotomy, lasik in situ keratomileusis) intra-ocular lens implants or a combination of these.^[7,8,9] The present case of a 23-year-old male who presented with a 5 year history of blurring of vision is being presented here. The patient was managed using *Sodhana kriyakalpa* and internal medication. He showed signs of visual improvement after treatment.

Ayurvedic Management, *Dipana-Pachana* drugs, *Snehapana*, *Shodhanachikista- Virechan* followed by *Nasya karma*. *Kriyakalpa* procedure like *Akshitarpana*, *Pindi*, *Seka* and Oral medications, different treatment principle is advised for this present case study evaluated the efficacy of *Kriyakalpa* procedure and Oral medication in managing Keratoconus w.s.r to *Prathama patalagata timira*.^[10]

CASE REPORT

CHIEF COMPLAINTS: A 23-year male patient approached Shalaky Tantra OPD of Mansarovar

OCULAR EXAMINATION

Table no.-1: Visual acuity test.

Distant vision	Right eye	Left eye
With out spectacles	6/18	6/24
With spectacles	6/6	6/9p 6/6
Near vision	N/6	N/6

Examinations of eye structure:

Table No.-2: Slit Lamp Examination.

structures	Right eye	Left eye
Conjunctiva	Normal	Normal
Sclera	Normal	Normal
Cornea - Size	Normal	Normal
Shape	bulge	bulge
Transparency	Clear	Clear
Surface	Normal	Normal
Anterior chamber	Normal	Normal
Iris	Normal	Normal
Pupil	Normal in shape and reacting to light	Normal in shape and reacting to light
Lens	Within normal limits	With in normal limits

Ayurvedic Medical College Hospital & Research Centre Bhopal, with complaints of blurring of vision for distant vision since 6 months of both eyes.

HISTORY OF PRESENT PATIENT: The patient was said to be apparently normal before 6 months. Gradually he developed blurring of vision in the both eyes, hence he approached our hospital for further medical management.

H/O PAST ILLNESS: The patient was diagnosed with B/L Keratoconus.

FAMILY HISTORY: No history of family illness.

PERSONAL HISTORY

Diet: Vegetarian

Appetite: Moderate

Bowel: Regular

Maturation: Normal

Sleep: Disturbed

Addiction: No any addiction

All vital signs and general physical examination were found to be within normal limit.

OCCUPATIONAL HISTORY: Patient was a student.

DIAGNOSTIC ASSESSMENT: 1. Based on chief complaints
2. Visual acuity findings
3 'K' value readings (mild <48D, Moderate 48D-54D, Severe >54D)

The treatment protocol followed was as follows

Table No.- 3: 1st Visit - Date 04/12/2023.

S.no.	Treatment	Dosage	Duration
1.	Nasya with shadbindu taila	4-4 each nostrils	5 days
2.	Kriyakalpa (Topical ocular therapeutics) Netra tarpan with Jeevantyadi Ghrita	Once daily	7 days
3.	Timiranjnam	1-1-1 in both eyes	30 days
4.	Rajatbhasma 125mg Giloyasatva 500mg Ashwagandha churna 2gm Saptamrit louha 250mg	Twice a day with honey before meal	30 days
5.	Tab. I- clear	1-1 tab. after meal	30 days
Second visit 15/01/24 Medicine 3 to 5 same for next 2 months.			

Table No.- 4: Third Visit Date 27/02/24.

Sr. No.	Medicine	Dose	Duration
1.	Netra raksha kashaya	20--20 ml	30 days
2.	E/d timiranjnam	1-1-1 drops in both eyes	15 days
3.	Yashtimadhu churna 20gm Haritaki churna 20gm Vibhitaki churna 20gm Amlaki churna 20gm Yashad bhasma 5gm Ashwagandha 15 gm	2gm-- --2gm with Triphala ghrita Before meal	30 days
4.	Tab.I-clear	1--1 tab. After meal	30 days

Table No.- 5 : Fourth Visit - Date 15/04/2024.

Sr.No.	Medicine	Dose	Duration
1.	Netra raksha kashaya	20 --- 20 ml before meal	30 days
2.	Saptamrit louha	2 ---- 2 after meal	30 days

Table No.- 6: Fifth visit date -21/06/24.

1.	Akshabeejadi Kashaya	20--20 ml with 1/2 cup of water, empty stomach	30 days
2.	Timiranjnam	1--1--1 drops in both eyes	30 days
3.	Tab.Timirex	Once a day after meal	30 days

Nasya karma: Drugs in the form of *Nasya* has probable mode of entry into circulation, helps in the improving vision. The drug absorption through mucous membrane, helps in direct pooling into venous sinuses of brain via inferior ophthalmic veins and absorption directly into the cerebrospinal fluid. As this, medicine is absorbed in ophthalmic vessels it helps in nourishing the extraocular muscles and eye proper. As the *shadbindu taila nasyais brumhana nasya* can be used in *vatapradhananetrarogas* and contains Antioxidant property helps in maintaining and building of the tissue.^[1]

Jeevantyadi Ghrita has high levels of antioxidant which can reduce corneal ectasia, strengthens the stromal collagen fibers by allowing more tissue contact time and bio availability of the drug from the corneal surface. As the *ghrita* contains more vitamin-A which helps in repairing the corneal epithelium.

Akshabeejadi kashaya & Netra raksha kashaya has Giloy (*Tinospora cordifolia*), Turmeric (*curcuma longa*), Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), Triphala-*Emblica officinalis* (Indian gooseberry), *Terminalia bellerica* (*Bibhitaki*),

and *Terminalia chebula* (*Haritaki*), *Brihathi* (*Solanum indicum*) & South Indian mahua (*Madhuca longifolia* var. *longifolia*), Liquorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*), Indian gooseberry (*Emblica officinalis*), Sappan wood, Grape fruit (*Citrus paradise*), and is indicated in all eye diseases. and is indicated in corneal disease, refractive errors, and other eye ailments. and is indicated in eye diseases. The internal medicines are aimed at *Tridoṣa Śamana* (pacification of all three Doshas), promoting eyesight, and maintenance of the corneal curvature.

Timiranjnam: it has all ingredients, provide strength to the eyes. Used in Ayurvedic formulations for its cleansing and detoxifying properties.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Symptoms significantly reduced after second seating of therapy and no side effect was observed during the treatment.

All these procedures and medication are having *chakshusya* and *balya* properties that's by they all are

provides strength and improve the functions of eye health.

CORNEAL TOPOGRAPHY FINDINGS

Table No.- 7 Before Treatment Readings.

Before Treatment Readings		
	OD	OS
K1(flat)	46.25 D	47.9 D
K2 (steep)	45.2 D	50.25 D
Pachy (apex)	482µm	462 µm
Thinnest local	476 µm	482 µm
Astigmatism(cornea front)	6.7D	7.2D

Table No.- 8 : After Treatment Readings.

After Treatment Readings		
	OD	OS
K1(flat)	46.2 D	47.5 D
K2 (steep)	44.3 D	47.9 D
Pachy (apex)	496 µm	476 µm
Thinnest local	490 µm	474 µm
Astigmatism (cornea front)	6.5 D	6.7 D

Table No.-9: Visual Acuity Test.

Visual acuity		Before treatment		After treatment	
		DV	NV	DV	NV
Unaided	RE	6/9p	N 6	6/9	N 6
	LE	6/12	N 9p	6/9	N 9
BCVA	RE	6/6	N6	6/6	N 6
	LE	6/9p	N9	6/6p	N 6p

Figures-1-4 Before And After Readings.

DISCUSSION

The symptoms of KC are similar to those observed in *Timira* of first *Patala* caused by vitiated *Vata* which gives rise to hazy and distorted vision. In this study, akshi *Basti* was selected as it does *Shodhana* and is also *Vatahara* and nourishing in nature. *Tarpan* was chosen as the chief line of treatment as it is said to provide strength to eyes.^[12,14]

The results were encouraging as there was improvement in visual acuity with reduction in symptoms and there was no progression of the disease which was confirmed by topographic profile repeated after treatment, which remained stable and also showed slight improvement.

Tarpana was advised in this case as it is said to be the best procedure to nourish the eye.

CONCLUSION

Keratoconus is a type of refractive error due to high degree of irregular astigmatism in this disease cornea becomes thin which can be understood as *karsyata*, it leads to thinning and protrusion of central part, as this part of corneal loss can be compared with *indriyadourbalya*, blurred vision is said to be *avyaktadarshanam*. According to Ayurveda it is considered as *Timira* the treatment should be followed as mentioned in *Samhita*, as the disease is progressive long-term treatment required. The Present case study showed that *Nasya*, *netra tarpan* therapy along with all oral medications had been found very effective in this case. Even through the limitations of this case study to a single study, this treatment modality may be an eye-opener for further studies as an effective management through Ayurveda in Keratoconus (*Timir*). Further study should be carried out in larger sample group.^[15,22]

INFORMED CONSENT: Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case.

PREVENTIVE MEASURES: Advice to maintain proper hygiene, Preventive measures like healthy balanced diet. Avoid stress by practicing yoga and meditation. The purpose of this study is to investigate the Ayurvedic approach to maintaining healthy eyesight, with a particular focus on both preventative and therapeutic approaches to the treatment of disorders that are associated with vision. Important Ayurvedic treatments and herbal eye care products are also covered in detail.

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